

➤ Preprints

What are they?

A preprint is a **scientific manuscript** that is uploaded by the authors to a **public server**

Why should I care?

Priority claim

By posting a preprint researchers can disclose their completed study immediately and without access barriers.¹

Increase citations

Articles get 36% more citations if they have a prior associated preprint.²

Receive feedback

Improve your manuscript by getting valuable comments on your research prior to publication.³

Proof of productivity

A preprint provides funders and hiring committees with public evidence of your work.⁴

Infographics by ASAPbio Fellows:

Ana Dorrego-Rivas (@adorrego_r), Carrie Iwema
and Mafalda Pimentel (@Maf_Pimentel)

➤ ASAPbio

Find more information at [ASAPbio.org](https://www.asapbio.org)

Sources:

1. Vale and Hyman. *eLife* 2016;5:e16931 doi: 10.7554/eLife.16931
2. Fu and Hughey. *eLife* 2019;8:e52646 doi: 10.7554/eLife.52646

3. Sever *et al.* bioRxiv 833400; doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/833400>
4. [asapbio.org/funder-policies](https://www.asapbio.org/funder-policies)

CC BY 4.0

